

Does corporate governance improve energy information disclosure among Nigeria listed manufacturing firms?

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the influence of corporate governance on energy information disclosure. Board size, CEO duality, institutional ownership, and foreign ownership are the measures of corporate governance used. A set of criteria derived from the Global Reporting Initiative is used to measure energy disclosure. An individual disclosure score is derived through content analysis of annual reports for a set of 60 manufacturing firms in Nigeria over 10 years, 2012-2021. Using a panel data regression model, we find that the presence of foreign ownership is the only determinant driving manufacturing firms to engage in energy disclosure behaviour. Energy disclosure is also more likely to be affected by factors unique to the company, such as firm size or whether or not it has been certified as meeting certain energy efficiency standards. Regulators should require manufacturing companies to include detailed financial and non-financial information on energy issues in their periodic report, and it should also place more emphasis on strengthening corporate governance, in order to improve energy disclosure.

Keywords:

Corporate Governance; Content Analysis; Energy Disclosure; Global Reporting Initiative; Manufacturing Firms; Nigeria.

1. Introduction

It is true that increased growth in the manufacturing sector has contributed to rise in economic growth and at the same time led to increase in energy problems. This led to a recognition on the part of the society that human well-being quality is degrading seriously. This increased awareness among various groups made corporations reduce their adverse impact of industrial activities on natural environment and also made them report the same in their periodic report. Thus, to meet the growing interest of the stakeholders, corporations have started involving themselves in 'responsible business' activities and disclosing the same to legitimise their business operations. However, companies were facing challenges in determining sustainable true profit as there were no accounting standards specifically designed to deal with energy issues. Consequently, many study groups have shown interest in developing guidelines on reporting energy information.¹ Those companies which have adopted these guidelines tend to portray their favourable and positive information in their periodic report. But socially conscious investors seek more accurate and reliable information not only about companies' financial returns but also corporate practices that promote social justice, energy sustainability and alternative energy/clean technology efforts. It is commonly argued that a good corporate governance is associated with increased transparency and credible disclosure to its stakeholders (Cormier et al., 2010; Gul & Leung, 2004).

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Thus, it is important to consider the level of energy reporting undertaken by a company, within the context of how the organisation is governed and controlled (Rao et al., 2012). While the linkage between corporate governance mechanism and firm performance is well established in several studies, little research has been conducted directly on examining the relationship between corporate governance and energy information disclosure in emerging market economies, and still very few studies address such relationships in Nigeria. Therefore, the present article investigates the impact of some characteristics of corporate governance on the energy disclosure of selected most polluting companies in Nigeria.

2. Literature Review and Hypotheses

2.1 Energy Information Disclosure

Energy reporting has been seen as one of the components of corporate social reporting (Hackston & Milne, 1996; Sahay, 2004). However, a number of attempts have been made to evaluate the status of energy accounting or disclosure as well as reporting practices of corporate organisations (Eugenio et al., 2010; Mathews, 1997, 2002; Owen, 2008; Parker, 2005). Many researchers have showed consistent interest in explaining how the business entities are responding to energy issues and to what extent they are disclosing the information (Ahmad & Mohamad, 2013; Bewley & Li, 2000; Cormier & Gordon, 2001; Freedman & Wasley, 1990; Llana et al., 2007; Wiseman, 1982).

It is observed that the disclosure behaviour is of low level, incomplete and inadequate to make sound investment decisions (Ahmad & Mohamad, 2013; D'Amico et al., 2016; Sahay, 2004; Yahaya, 2018). Some studies have confirmed that the level of energy disclosures varies across industries (Cormier & Gordon, 2001; Monteiro & Aibar-Guzman, 2010; Sen et al., 2011; Yahaya, 2018) and also between countries (Buhr & Freedman, 2001; Cowan & Gadenne, 2005). They observed that the variations in volume of disclosures are due to differences in statutory framework prevailing in a country, according to which companies are required to disclose energy information in their periodic reports.

2.2 Theoretical Approach

A number of theoretical approaches have been used to explain rationale of companies to disclose social responsibility information (Gray et al., 1995; Yahaya & Lamido, 2022), however, majority of the literature lend its support to agency theory and legitimacy theory (Onwe et al., 2020; Yahaya & Andow, 2015; Yahaya et al., 2017; Yahaya & Tijjani, 2021). Agency theory provides a framework linking disclosure behaviour to corporate governance and it suggests that monitoring or agency costs arise from the conflicts of interests between shareholders and managers (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Shareholders of the company mostly rely on their agents as they do not have thorough financial knowledge. Managers who have better access to a firm's internal information can reduce its agency cost by providing fair and credible communication to its stakeholders (Barako et al., 2006; Halme & Huse, 1997). Energy information disclosures are voluntarily done by the managers to inform its shareholders about the energy practices and activities undertaken by the company (Chaklader & Gulati, 2015). Thus, it can be expected that energy information disclosure reduces agency cost which arises from the conflicts between shareholders and managers. Another important theory that explains the motivation of companies to disclose energy information is legitimacy theory. It suggests that energy information disclosure is used as a strategy to communicate with its stakeholders and convinces them that the company is fulfilling their social responsibility (Cho & Patten, 2007; Clarkson et al., 2008; Cormier & Gordon, 2001; Gray et al., 1995; Haniffa & Cooke, 2005; Nurhayati et al., 2015; Ortas et al., 2014; Patten, 2002; Wilmshurst & Frost, 2000).

2.3 Corporate Governance and Energy Information Disclosure

Since the 1990s, there have been a number of studies which identified factors associated with energy information disclosure. Majority of the studies concentrated on firm-specific characteristics such as company size, industry type, profitability, foreign association, listing on stock exchange, leverage, ownership status, age of company and energy certification. Besides these characteristics, some studies have examined the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and the level of energy disclosures.

Halme and Huse (1997) examine the association between corporate energy reporting and corporate governance variable for a sample of 140 Scandinavian listed companies (Finland, Norway, Sweden and Spain). The corporate governance variables used in the study are ownership concentration and board size. The study observes varying relationship between variables due to differing corporate governance prevailing among the four countries. Eng and Mak (2003) examine the impact of various forms of ownership structure and board composition on voluntary disclosure of 158 Singapore companies. The study finds that lower managerial ownership and significant government ownership are associated with increased disclosure, whereas block holder ownership is not related to disclosure practices. The study also reveals that an increase in outside directors reduces corporate disclosure.

Barako et al. (2006) examine the influence of corporate governance variables on voluntary disclosure by using a sample of 43 Kenyan companies. The study identifies the presence of audit committee, the level of institutional and foreign ownership having a significant positive impact on voluntary disclosure and the proportion of independent non-executive directors (INEDs) on the board, which is found to be negatively associated. Buniamin et al. (2008) examine whether board independence, chief executive officer (CEO) duality, management ownership and board size have any association with the companies' energy disclosure in annual reports of 243 Malaysian companies. Findings from the study reveal that only board size has a significant relationship with energy reporting.

Donnelly and Mulcahy (2008) examine the relationship between voluntary disclosure and corporate governance mechanisms for a sample of 51 Irish companies. The study finds that increase in the institutional and management ownership associates with increased voluntary disclosure. Rao et al. (2012) investigate the relationship between energy reporting and corporate governance mechanisms of 96 Australian companies. The study finds positive relationship between the extent of energy reporting and the proportion of INEDs and female directors on the board.

The prior literature shows that only few studies have investigated the relationship between corporate governance and energy information disclosure. Most of them have been centred around developed countries, while very few concentrated on developing countries. In the Nigerian context, there are a limited number of studies which have explored the status of energy information disclosure (Chizobi & Mir, 2008; Mathew & Yadav, 2009; Sahabi, 2004; Sene et al., 2011) and its determinants (Chukwu & Gulati, 2015; Jose et al., 2011; Makoju & Jagongo, 2013; Peters, 2009), whereas Nuruman et al. (2015) have made an attempt to investigate the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and energy information disclosure. All these studies are based on samples of top-listed companies and core sector companies. Hence, it is observed from the above literature that there has been no study particularly on the impact of corporate governance mechanisms on energy information disclosure of manufacturing corporations in Nigeria.

2.4 Hypotheses

The role of board is to align the behaviour of the corporation, ensure compliance with legal framework and maintain credibility in the eyes of stakeholders through timely disclosure (Fama & Jensen, 1983; Hill & Jones, 1992; Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Yahaya & Tijani, 2020). The number of directors on the board, that is, board size plays an important role in monitoring the management's

performance. Empirical evidence on the board size and management's performance came up with mixed results where some studies argued in favour of smaller sized board, suggesting that it can monitor the management effectively as it can take a unanimous decision easily (Cheng, 2008; Ienciu, 2012; Kassins & Vafeas, 2002; Walls et al., 2012; Yahaya & Apochi, 2021). On the contrary, some studies argue that larger sized board depicts that there is a broader range of stakeholders with necessary experience and expertise that leads to higher firm performance (Dalton et al., 1999; Halme & Huse, 1997; Jegede et al., 2018). Some studies relate board size to energy information disclosure; majority of them identify positive association, suggesting that a larger board possesses necessary expertise and experience to provide energy advice (Buniamin et al., 2008; Rao et al., 2012; Yahaya, 2006; Yahaya & Andow, 2015; Yahaya, 2019) and access energy opportunities of firms (Villiers et al., 2011). Considering this, it is hypothesised that:

H₁: Board size is positively associated with energy information disclosure.

CEO duality means that a director holds the position of the CEO and chairman of the board at the same time. If the director has dominance over the board, the director may have the freedom to withhold the company's unfavourable information and disclose only positive information to its investors (Chau & Gray, 2010). Besides, CEO duality reduces board's monitoring ability (Fama & Jensen, 1983) which is detrimental to the quality of disclosure (Forker, 1992). Empirical studies find that CEO duality is associated with low level of corporate disclosures (Forker, 1992; Gul & Leung, 2004; Yahaya et al., 2017; Yahaya & Tijani, 2020; Yahaya, 2022a, 2022b). Based on the literature, it is expected that the CEO duality negatively relates with the extent of energy disclosure and it is hypothesised that:

H₂: CEO duality is negatively associated with energy information disclosure.

A domestic institutional investor who owns large blocks of company's equity share can have greater ability in acquiring internal information. Having access to all the essential information they need, an institutional investor can better monitor management activities and pressurise the management to keep public disclosure to the minimum (Laidroo, 2009). On the one hand, empirical studies on this issue found mixed results where some studies support positive association, stating that the monitoring role of institutional investors would motivate companies to report disclosure of higher quality financial as well as non-financial information (Barako et al., 2006; Chau & Gray, 2010; Iatridis, 2013; Laidroo, 2009; Rao et al., 2012). On the other hand, some studies support negative association, stating that institutional investors are less likely to demand public disclosure as they can easily access internal information (Donnelly & Mulcahy, 2008; Lakhal, 2005; Yahaya & Awen, 2021). In addition to this, Barker (cited in Donnelly & Mulcahy, 2008) and Eng and Mak (2003) evidence that institutional owners depend on information that is released through formal meeting rather the public disclosure, that is, annual report. Since the present study considers annual report as source of data, it is expected that institutional ownership will have negative association with the energy information disclosure. Thus, the following hypothesis is proposed for testing:

H₃: Institutional ownership is negatively associated with energy information disclosure.

Companies in which foreigners hold majority of shares may demand higher quality of corporate financial reporting in order to meet foreign reporting requirements (Barako et al., 2006). Similarly, it is possible that this group of investors can influence energy disclosures since they require information on energy risks and protection activities and measures taken to conserve energy (Barako et al., 2006; Haniffa & Cooke, 2002; Pahuja, 2009; Yahaya, 2022). Based on the literature, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H₄: Foreign ownership is positively associated with energy information disclosure.

3. Methodology

Many studies have documented that industry type that is manufacturing firms appear to be significantly variable in explaining energy information disclosure (Brammer & Pavelin, 2008; Burgwal & Vieira, 2014; D'Amico et al., 2016; Dragomir, 2010; Hackston & Milne, 1996; Halme & Huse, 1997; Pahuja, 2009). Considering this, sample of the study is drawn from manufacturing sector as categorised by the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX). The sample of the study comprises of 60 manufacturing firms and the period of coverage is 10 years (2012-2021). The energy information disclosure used content analysis is measured on the basis of certain themes related to energy information. Researchers have adopted a different checklist of items to capture energy information. This study measures the extent of energy disclosures by framing a list of items called as energy disclosure Index (EDI) which is primarily based on Global Reporting Initiative (GRI 3.1) and also on information pertaining to energy regulations prevailing in Nigeria. EDI consists of 47 items which encompass general as well as specific energy information. It is measured by assigning unequal dummy score depending on the existence and specificity of information; where '2' is assigned to detail or monetary information of the item, '1' is assigned to limited information and '0' is assigned to no information about the item. For example, if a company already has a separate department for energy management system, score '2' is assigned. But if they are planning to do it in the near future, score '1' is assigned or otherwise '0'. If a company reviews its energy policy, then score '1' is given or otherwise '0'. Further, if the statement prepared by a company is audited by the big4 external auditor, score '2' is given. But in case these have been audited by non big4 external auditor, score '1' is given or otherwise '0'. In the same way, differential scores are assigned to each item within a sub-classification. Thus, overall maximum possible score comes to 80. The value of EDI is calculated for each firm as the ratio of computed total disclosure score to the maximum possible score and then it is expressed in percentage. EDI is the energy disclosure index of company i at t period.

The EDI may vary between 0 and 100 per cent. On the one hand, the value near 100 per cent indicates that the company is concerned to disclose the requisite energy information on all counts of EDI. On the other hand, the value near 0 indicates that the company does not have interest in disclosing energy information and it shows the reluctance of the company on this issue.

In order to test previously formulated hypotheses, the following independent variables are measured: *Board size* (BS) is measured by counting total number of directors on board. Board size dummy (BS_D) is measured by binary value. Considering the median value of BS, the sample is separated into a large board where the firm has eight and above directors and are assigned score '1' and a small board where the firm has below eight directors and are assigned score '0'. *CEO duality* (CED_D) is measured by assigning dummy variable of '1' if the firm's CEO is also the chairman of the board of directors or otherwise '0'. *Institutional ownership* (IO) is measured by employing percentage of equity ownership held by domestic institutional investor. *Foreign ownership* (FO) is measured by employing percentage of equity ownership held by a foreign institutional investor.

The control variables of the study are measured as follows:

Profitability (P) is measured by employing return on assets. *Company size* (CS) is measured by using natural logarithm of total assets. Considering the median value of CS, company size dummy (CSD) is measured by binary value. The median value of CS is 5.215; the firm which has value of 5.215 and above is considered a large company and assigned value of '1' or otherwise '0'. *energy certification* (EC) is measured by a dummy variable, where '1' is assigned to a company that possesses energy certification, that is, the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 14000, or otherwise '0'. To find out the appropriate panel data regression model, the study has undertaken Breusch-Pagan test and Hausman test which clearly support the *random effects model* for both equations (2) and (3).

The panel data test statistics results are shown in Table 1. The following regression model has been used to test the hypotheses:

$$EDI_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 BS_{i,t} + \beta_2 BSD_{i,t} + \beta_3 CEOD_{i,t} + \beta_4 IO_{i,t} + \beta_5 FO_{i,t} + \beta_6 P_{i,t} + \beta_7 CS_{i,t} + \beta_8 CSD_{i,t} + \beta_9 EC_{i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas: EDI is the energy disclosure index, *i* is the firm indicator, *t* is the period indicator, BS is the board size, CEOD is CEO duality, IO is the institutional ownership, FO is the foreign ownership, P is the return on assets, CS is the natural logarithm of total assets and EC is energy certification where BSD is the board size dummy and CSD is the company size dummy.

Table 1. Regression Results of Model Variables

Variables	Coefficients	Z statistics	Adj. R ²	Wald chi ²	VIF
Const	10.111	0 7.12**			–
BSD	0.519	1.12			1.22
CEOD	1.837	1.25			1.042
IO	0.017	0.39			1.571
FO	0.167	0 3.7**	30.09	108.82**	1.52
P	1.4	0 2.05*			1.38
CSD	0.009	0.55*			1.05
EC	4.745	0 8.99**			1.328

Breush–Pagan LM test 2117.66 (0.0000) and Hausman test 27.21 (0.103)

Breush–Pagan LM test 2033.72 (0.0000) and Hausman test 32.83 (0.137)

Source: Computed by the authors.

Notes: ** indicates significance at 1 per cent level and * significance at 5 per cent level.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 2 presents descriptive statistics of the present study. The basic purpose of descriptive statistics is to explore the empirical distribution of the variables used in the study. It can be stated from the table that the average level of disclosure is 14.82 per cent and reveals that the extent of energy disclosure of manufacturing companies in Nigeria is limited. The minimum and maximum values of EDI show that the sample companies, except for a few, failed to disseminate complete and comprehensive energy information to its stakeholders. The result of the study is consistent with Sahay (2004) who observes that energy disclosures by Nigerian corporations are still in infancy stage and it lags significantly behind as found in the developed countries except for a few companies. However, the year-wise disclosure level shows increasing trend (shown in Figure 2) and suggests that selected sample companies should have some level of energy disclosure in their annual reports. Further, the figure reveals that there is a sizeable increase in the year 2012–2013 as a result of inclusion of BR reports. It is disheartening to note that only 8 per cent of the sample companies included BR reports in their annual reports.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of the Model Variables

Particulars	Min	Mean	Median	Max	Std. Dev.
EDI	0	14.83	11.25	98.75	14.13
BS	3	8.55	8	19	3.05
IO	0	4.02	0.38	40.83	6.54
FO	0	3.86	0	34.92	7.17
P	–54.06	1.53	0.07	205.97	11.28
CS	–0.45	5.32	5.22	12.63	2.90
CEOD:	Sep: 70%	EC: Yes: 40%			
	Same: 30%	No: 60%			

Source: Computed by the authors

It is also observed from the content analysis of the study that 40.86 per cent of the sample companies disclosed information pertaining to energy regulations prevailing in Nigeria and only 8 per cent of sample companies adopted GRI framework to disclose energy information. This shows that most of the companies do not show initiatives to incorporate stand-alone report or sustainability report, the reason being that it incurs extra cost burden to them to produce such information. It is also observed from the study that the liberal nature of framework made most of the companies to disseminate general and positive information in their annual report.

Further, Table 3 depicts that the board size ranges from minimum of 3 to maximum of 19 directors on the board. The institutional investor holds an average of 4.02 per cent of equity share, minimum of 0 and maximum of 40.83 per cent of equity share. The foreign investor holds an average of 3.86 per cent of equity share, minimum of 0 and maximum of 34.92 per cent of equity share. Profitability of the sample companies measured as return on assets varies from -54.06 kobo to 205.97 kobo Nigerian naira. The size of the companies measured as natural logarithm of total assets ranges from -0.45 kobo to 12.63 kobo Nigerian naira. From the firm year observations, 70 per cent of the CEOs are separate from the chairman of the board and 40 per cent of observations possess energy certification, that is, ISO 14000.

Table 2 shows the results of the panel data regression model carried out in this study. The adjusted R^2 gives 39.27 (for equation 2) and 30.09 (for equation 3) percent of variation in EDI are explained by the independent and other three control variables. The model appears to be *goodness of fit* as the *Wald chi²* for both regression equations are significant at 1 per cent level. Further, a cursory look into variance inflation factor (VIF) results showed in the table depicts that variables are not highly correlated among one other, therefore, the severity of collinearity problem is expected to be low.

The coefficient of board size is positively significant at 1 per cent level. The result of the study is consistent with Halme and Huse (1997), Buniamin et al. (2008) and Rao et al. (2012). But the coefficient estimate of board size dummy is not significant to support the positive association as predicted in H_1 . This result is consistent with Kassins and Vafeas (2002), Cheng (2008), Ienciu (2012) and Walls et al. (2012) who supported the board with large number of directors is not very effective as there is ineffectual communication and higher coordination costs that lead to free rider problems (Guest, 2009). In addition to this, Lipton and Lorsch (1992) and Jensen (cited in Guest, 2009) argue that the board size that is greater than 8 or 9 can worsen the firm performance as well as represent poor governance.

The coefficient of CEO duality is found to be insignificant to support H_2 . The result of the study is consistent with Ho and Wong (2001), Buniamin et al. (2008) and Kelton and Yang (2008) who identify that there is no relationship between CEO duality and the extent of energy disclosure practice.

The coefficient of institutional ownership is found to be insignificant to support H_3 . The result of the study is consistent with Donnelly and Mulcahy (2008) who observed that there is no relationship between the two variables and stated that this may be due to the reason that institutional investors are passive with respect to the disclosure of information contained in public disclosure, that is, the annual report.

The variable foreign ownership is found to be positively significant to support positive association as predicted in H_4 . The result of the study is consistent with Haniffa and Cooke (2002) and Barako et al. (2006) who support that companies in which foreigners hold more number of shares influence not only company's financial performance but also voluntary disclosure with higher social value.

The study also finds that there is no association between energy disclosures and profitability of the company. The results are consistent with Hacktson and Milne (1996), Brammer and Pavelin (2008), Monteiro and Aibar-Guzman (2010), Chaklader and Gulati (2015) and D'Amico et al. (2016) who identify that there is no relationship between profitability and disclosure practices.

The coefficient of company size and company size dummy are found to be positive and significant to support that larger companies disclose more energy information in their annual report. The result is consistent with the existing literature (Andrikopoulos & Krikiani, 2013; Burgwal & Vieira, 2014; Chaklader & Gulati, 2015; Cormier & Gordon, 2001; D'Amico et al., 2016; Deegan & Gordon, 1996; Hackton & Milne, 1996; Ortas et al., 2014; Pahuja, 2009; Roberts, 1991) which documents that big companies can afford the cost of producing energy information to reduce public pressure.

The analysis also shows that companies which possess energy certification are positively associated with energy disclosure practices. The result of the study is consistent with findings of Monteiro and Aibar-Guzman (2010) and Chukwu and Gulati (2015) who reveal that energy certification reduces the agency or monitoring cost since the firm voluntarily follows energy norms and guidelines set by energy rating agency.

5. Conclusion

Highly energy usage companies are gradually realising that incorporating 'responsible business' activities adds on value to their corporation as well as it wins the trust of the general public. The present study is an attempt to examine the energy disclosure status and impact of corporate governance on such disclosure for a sample of 60 manufacturing companies in Nigeria. At first, the article examines the extent of energy disclosures and states that disclosures are limited. But the year-wise energy disclosure shows an increasing trend, suggesting that firms in Nigeria realise the importance of such reporting practices and these will improve in the near future. The study also finds that companies which are concerned with energy are very less due to the lenient framework on energy usage regulations prevailing in Nigeria.

The primary focus of the study is to examine the impact of corporate governance mechanisms on energy information disclosure. Corporate governance mechanisms appear to have an effect on the energy disclosures of manufacturing corporations in Nigeria. The study finds that a board with large number of directors makes the governance ineffective that leads to less energy disclosure. The study further observes that companies in which foreigners hold majority of shares significantly influence energy disclosures to meet foreign reporting requirements. It is also observed from the study that large companies disclose more energy information than others as they have more stakeholders and that disclosing such information will legitimise their business operation, reduce public pressure as well as create a corporate image. Further, companies that obtain energy certification from an independent agency will also disclose more information as they voluntarily follow energy norms and guidelines compared to other firms. This will add value to the firm and its product; it also wins the trust and goodwill of its stakeholders to survive in the long run and compete with their competitors. Overall result of the study supports that the companies use energy disclosure as strategy to legitimise their business operation as well as to reduce agency problems to an extent. The findings of the present study suggest that regulators should mandate stringent regulations for all heavy energy user-companies to disclose detailed monetary and non-monetary energy related information in its periodic report. Further, to create active and effective corporate governance the regulators should reduce the maximum number of directors on the board and also make it compulsory that at least two of the board members should have better knowledge to deal energy issues.

References

- Ahmad, N. N., & Mohamad, N. A. (2013). *Corporate social responsibility and energy management*. Retrieved 21 January 2014, from www.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/csr.1322/pdf.
- Ajibulu, E. G., Yahaya, O. A., & Agbi, S. E. (2021). Board of directors and quality of financial reports of quoted banks: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Finance Research*, 1(1), 79-99.
- Aliyu, A. B., Yahaya, O. A., & Mohammed, N. A. (2021), Board features and financial performance of Nigerian banks. *International Journal of Finance and Banking Studies*, 10(1), 11-19.

- Barako, D. G., Hancock, P., & Izan, H. Y. (2006). Factors influencing voluntary corporate disclosure by Kenyan companies. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 14(2), 107–125.
- Bewley, K., & Li, Y. (2000). Disclosure of energy information by Canadian manufacturing companies: A voluntary disclosure perspective. *Advances in Energy Accounting & Management*, 1, 201–226.
- Brammer, S., & Pavelin, S. (2008). Factors influencing the quality of corporate energy disclosure. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 17(2), 120–136.
- Buhr, N., & Freedman, M. (2001). Culture, institutional factors and difference in energy disclosure between Canada and the United States. *Critical Perspectives on Accounting*, 12(3), 293–322.
- Buniamin, S., Alrazi, B., Johari, N. H., & Rahman, N. R. (2008). An investigation of the association between corporate governance and energy reporting in Malaysia. *Asian Journal of Business and Accounting*, 1(2), 65–88.
- Burgwal, D. V., & Vieira, R. J. (2014). Energy disclosure determinants in Dutch listed companies. *Revista Contabilidade & Finanças*, 25(64), 60–78.
- Chaklader, B., & Gulati, P. A. (2015). A study of corporate energy disclosure practices of companies doing business in Nigeria. *Global Business Review*, 16(2), 321–335.
- Chatterjee, B., & Mir, M. Z. (2008). The current status of energy reporting by Nigerian companies. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 23(6), 609–629.
- Chau, G., & Gray, S. J. (2010). Family ownership, board independence and voluntary disclosure: Evidence from Hong Kong. *J. of Int. Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, 19(3), 93–109.
- Cheng, S. (2008). Board size and the variability of corporate performance. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 87(1), 157–176.
- Cho, C. H., & Patten, D. M. (2007). The role of energy disclosures as tools of legitimacy: A research note. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 32(7–8), 639–647.
- Clarkson, P. M., Li, Y., Richardson, G. D., & Vasvari, F. P. (2008). Revisiting the relation between energy performance and energy disclosure: An empirical analysis. *Accounting, Organisation and Society*, 33(4–5), 303–327.
- Cormier, D., & Gordon, I. M. (2001). An examination of social and energy reporting strategies. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 14(5), 587–616.
- Cormier, D., Ledoux, M., & Magnan, M. (2010). Corporate governance and information asymmetry between managers and investors. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 10(5), 574–589.
- Cowan, S., & Gadenne, D. (2005). Australian corporate energy reporting: A comparative analysis of disclosure practices across voluntary and mandatory disclosure systems. *Journal of Accounting & Organizational Change*, 1(2), 165–179.
- Dalton, D., Daily, C., Johnson, J., & Ellstrand, A. (1999). Number of directors and financial performance: A meta-analysis. *Academy of Management Journal*, 42(6), 674–686.
- D'Amico, E., Coluccia, D., Fontana, S., & Solimene, S. (2016). Factors influencing corporate energy disclosure. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 25(3), 178–192.
- Deegan, C., & Gordon, B. (1996). A study of the energy disclosure practices of Australian corporations. *Accounting and Business Research*, 26(3), 187–199.
- Donnelly, R., & Mulcahy, M. (2008). Board structure, ownership, and voluntary disclosure in Ireland. *Corporate Governance*, 16(5), 416–429.
- Dragomir, V. D. (2010). Energy sensitive disclosures and financial performance in a European setting. *Journal of Accounting & Organizational Change*, 6(3), 359–388.
- Eng, L., & Mak, Y. (2003). Corporate governance and voluntary disclosure. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 22(4), 325–345.
- Eugenio, T., Lourenco, I. C., & Morais, A. I. (2010). Recent developments in social and energy accounting research. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 6(2), 286–305.

- Fama, E. F., & Jensen, M. (1983). Separation of ownership and control. *Journal of Law and Economics*, 26(2), 301–326.
- Forker, J. R. (1992). Corporate governance and disclosure quality. *Accounting and Business Research*, 22(86), 111–124.
- Freedman, M., & Wasley, C. (1990). The association between energy performance and energy disclosure in annual reports and 10-Ks. *Advances in Public Interest Accounting*, 3(2), 183–193.
- Gray, R., Kouhy, R., & Lavers, S. (1995). Corporate social and energy reporting: A review of the literature and a longitudinal study UK disclosure. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 8(2), 47–77.
- Guest, P. M. (2009). The impact of board size on firm performance: Evidence from the UK. *The European Journal of Finance*, 15(4), 385–404.
- Gul, F. A., & Leung, S. (2004). Board leadership, outside directors' expertise and voluntary corporate disclosures. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 23(5), 351–379.
- Hackston, D., & Milne, M. J. (1996). Some determinants of social and energy disclosures in New Zealand companies. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 9(1), 77–108.
- Halme, M., & Huse, M. (1997). The influence of corporate governance, industry and country factors on energy reporting. *Scandinavian Journal of Management*, 13(2), 137–157.
- Haniffa, R. M., & Cooke, T. E. (2002). Culture, corporate governance and disclosure in Malaysian corporations. *Abacus*, 38(3), 317–349.
- Hill, C. W., & Jones, T. M. (1992). Stakeholder-agency theory. *Journal of Management Studies*, 29(2), 131–154.
- Ho, S. S., & Wong, K. S. (2001). A study of the relationship between corporate governance structures and the extent of voluntary disclosure. *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, 10(2), 139–156.
- Iatridis, G. E. (2013). Energy disclosure quality: Evidence on energy performance, corporate governance and value relevance. *Emerging Markets Review*, 14, 55–75.
- Ienciu, I. A. (2012). The relationship energy reporting and corporate governance characteristics of Romanian listed companies. *Acc. and Management Information Systems*, 11(2), 267–294.
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs, and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305–365.
- Joshi, P. L., Suwaidan, M. S., & Kumar, R. (2011). Determinants of energy disclosures by Nigerian industrial listed companies in their websites: Empirical study. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 3(2), 109–130.
- Kassinis, G., & Vafeas, N. (2002). Corporate boards and outside stakeholders as determinants of energy litigation. *Strategic Management Journal*, 23(5), 399–415.
- Kelton, A. S., & Yang, Y. W. (2008). The impact of corporate governance on Internet financial reporting. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 27(1), 62–87.
- Laidroo, L. (2009). Association between ownership structure and public announcements' disclosures. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 17(1), 13–34.
- Lakhal, F. (2005). Voluntary earnings disclosures and corporate governance: Evidence from France. *Review of Accounting & Finance*, 4(3), 64–86.
- Lipton, M., & Lorsch, J. W. (1992). A modest proposal for improved corporate governance. *The Business Lawyer*, 48(1), 59–78.
- Llena, F., Moneva, J. M., & Hernandez, B. (2007). Energy disclosures and compulsory accounting standards: The case of Spanish annual reports. *Bus. Strategy & the Environment*, 16(1), 50–63.
- Makori, D. M., & Jagongo, A. (2013). Energy accounting and firm profitability: An empirical analysis of selected firms listed in Bombay Stock Exchange. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(18), 248–256.

- Malarvizhi, P., & Yadav, S. (2009). Corporate energy disclosures on the internet: An empirical analysis of Nigerian companies. *Issues in Social and energy Accounting*, 2(2), 211–232.
- Mathews, M. R. (1997). Twenty-five years of social and energy accounting research: Is there a silver jubilee to celebrate? *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 10(4), 481–531.
- Mathews, M. R. (2002). *The development of social and energy accounting research 1995–2000*. Retrieved 2 January 2014, from <http://mro.massey.ac.nz/bitstream/handle/10179/2548/205.pdf>
- Monteiro, S. M., & Aibar-Guzman, B. (2010). Determinants of energy disclosure in the annual reports of large companies operating in Portugal. *Corporate Social Responsibility and energy Management*, 17(4), 185–204.
- Nurhayati, R., Taylor, G., & Tower, G. (2015). Investigating social and energy disclosure practices by listed Nigerian textile firms. Proceedings of the Australasian Conference on Business and Social Sciences). *The Journal of Developing Areas*, Sydney, 201–212.
- Onwe, E. D., Mustapha, L. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2020). Financial structure and financial performance of listed firms in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 11(14), 120-136.
- Ortas, E., Gallego-Alvarez, I., & Etxeberria, I. A. (2014). Financial factors influencing the quality of corporate social responsibility and energy management disclosure: A quantile regression approach. *Corporate Social Responsibility and energy Management*, 22(6), 362–380.
- Owen, D. (2008). Chronicles of wasted time? A personal reflection on the current state of, and future prospects for, social and energy accounting research. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 21(2), 240–267.
- Pahuja, S. (2009). Relationship between energy disclosures and corporate characteristics: A study of large manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 5(2), 227–244.
- Parker, L. D. (2005). Social and energy accountability research: A view from the commentary box. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 18(6), 842–860.
- Patten, D. M. (2002). The relation between energy performance and energy disclosure: A research note. *Accounting, Organisations and Society*, 27(8), 763–773.
- Rao, K. K., Tilt, C. A., & Lester, L. H. (2012). Corporate governance and energy reporting: An Australian study. *Corporate Governance*, 12(2), 143–163.
- Roberts, C. B. (1991). energy disclosures: A note on reporting practices in mainland Europe. *Accounting Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 4(3), 62–71.
- Sahay, A. (2004). energy reporting by Nigerian corporations. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Energy Management*, 11(1), 12–22.
- Sene, M., Mukherjee, K., & Pattanayak, J. K. (2011). Corporate energy disclosure practices in Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 12(2), 139–156.
- Villiers, C. D., Naiker, V., & Staden, C. J. (2011). The effect of board characteristics on firm energy performance. *Journal of Management*, 37(6), 1636–1663.
- Walls, J. L., Berrone, P., & Phan, P. H. (2012). Corporate governance and energy performance: Is there really a link? *Strategic Management Journal*, 33(8), 885–913.
- Wilmshurst, T. D., & Frost, G. R. (2000). Corporate energy reporting: A test of legitimacy theory. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 13(1), 10–26.
- Wiseman, J. W. (1982). An evaluation of energy disclosures made in corporate annual reports. *Accounting, Organisation & Society*, 7(1), 53–63.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2006). Empirical evidence on the effect of size on the profitability of Nigerian commercial banks. *Journal of Social Studies*, 11(4), 33-39.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2018). Environmental reporting practices and financial performance of environmentally-sensitive firms in Nigeria. *Savanna: A Journal of the Environmental and Social Sciences*, 6(16), 136-146.

- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., & Tijjani, B. (2019). Financial mix and financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Management*, 2(1), 226-237.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Andow, H. A. (2015). Capital structure and firm's financial performance: Panel evidence of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. *Kaduna Business Management Review*, 2(1), 45-56.
- Yahaya, O. A., Tanko, M., & Liman, M. L. (2017). Effects of corporate characteristics on earnings quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Kaduna State University Journal of Management Sciences*, 8(1), 47-64.
- Yahaya, O. A., Tijani, B. (2020). Internal corporate governance and intellectual capital of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Review*, 8(9), 98-112.
- Yahaya, O. A., Awen, B. I. (2021). Chief executive officers and bankruptcy of quoted resources companies in Nigeria. *Fountain Journal of Management Sciences*, 10(2), 970-980.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Tijjani, B. (2021). Size, age and leverage of Nigeria quoted oil and gas corporations. *Advanced Int. Journal of Banking, Accounting and Finance*, 3(6), 51-60.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEOs influence earnings management? *South African Journal of Accounting Research*, 36(2), 1-13.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Lamido, I. A. (2022). Corporate social responsibility and financial performance: evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance Review*, 10(1), 107-120.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. G. (2022). The board of directors' influence on the intellectual capital of Nigeria's listed firms. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing & Finance*, 37(2), 1-17.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Does board of directors improve profitability? *Accounting*, 8(2022), 269-275.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does board gender diversity influence dividend pay-out? Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance and Risk Management*, 7(2), 25-53.
- Yahaya, O. A., Mohammed, I., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Board governance and sustainability disclosure of Nigeria listed deposit money banks. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(5), 126-147.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Corporate governance and profitability: An application of agency theory. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 34(2), 406-421.